

CRITERIA AND LEVELS OF GLOBAL PROBLEMS

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Annotation: This article is happening all over our country information about acute problems and conflicts is given.

Key words: tension, importance, generality, problems, consistency, demographic politics, social tension, social illiteracy.

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An important feature of global problems is that they are all related to each other depends to such an extent that solving one of them at least creates other problems for him means taking into account the effect. Listed criteria of global problems and characteristic features of most researchers in this field reflects the views and differentiates global problems from all other problems, allows you to say clearly. This is the tension and importance of this or that problem to determine its level, to determine its interrelationship with other problems different classifications are usually made, they are divided into separate groups. Classification is not the only goal, but rather the extreme of the current era acts as an important element of the complex study of conflicts problems in terms of their interrelationship and mutual dependence allows learning. It is important to differentiate relationships, priorities and objective allows to determine the degree of exacerbation of existing global problems. In addition, the classification enhances the systematic interrelationship of global problems It helps to understand more deeply and the sequence of making practical decisions It helps to determine. Know the classification that is done consistently and accurately to a certain extent summarizes the previous researches in this field and at the same time notes the beginning of a new stage in the development of such research.

Current between different approaches to the classification of global problems at the time especially according to the widely recognized classification of global problems, all of them the level of tension and the importance of the solution, as well as their in real life divided into three large groups depending on the causal connections between them. The first group is characterized by the greatest degree of commonality and importance problems. They arise from relations between different countries. That's it therefore they are called intersocial global problems. Here from community life eliminating war and ensuring a just world; a new international economic order Two very important problems such as installation are distinguished: The second group is society and are problems that arise as a result of the interaction of nature, and they affect people supply of energy, fuel, fresh water, raw material resources, etc are like This group includes environmental problems, as well as the world's oceans and space mastery of space is also included. The third group is related to the "human-society" system problems, i.e. demography problem, health care, education, international terrorism the threat is spiritual issues and the like. This or that problem is specific inclusion in the group acquires a conditional character to a certain extent and depends on important factors, depends on the basis of their separation. Therefore, any classification is problematic not as a short-term solution, but to reorganize a complex system contribute to a better understanding of the interconnected nature of global problems should be considered as one of the methods. Now a serious threat to all humanity we will give a brief description of the most important problems. Main global problem system. The global problems of the present time are constantly changing their situation in time is the only, active and open system that changes, because it is universal the introduction of new important problems, and the previous problems are theirs depending on the solution, it may disappear. Founder and first president of the Club of Rome A.Pechchei paid attention to this situation and was against humanity most of the problems are "caught up in each other, a giant sprue clutch news is gripping the entire planet... the number of unsolved problems is growing are becoming more complex, their complexity is greater are getting tangled

up, and their "scoundrel" is holding our planet more and more in its grip is squeezing harder", wrote 1. But how much a node of global conflicts no matter how complicated it is, it is important to solve it with the help of science and philosophy, that is, to distinguish the cause from the effect to distinguish detail from secondary detail, objective from subjective it is necessary to understand theoretically. Impact on global processes taking into account the limited capabilities and resources of people for which problems require immediate solution and which are secondary it is also important to distinguish between importance. Demographic problem. Nowadays among the most important problems of humanity, in most countries and regions population growth, which causes overpopulation, is noted will be done. According to the estimates of some experts, the energy available on the planet, raw materials, food and other resources on Earth only about one billion people ("gold billion") can ensure a decent life. However, the last thousand The population of our planet has increased 15 times over the years and today it is 6 billion exceeded a person. In this case, not only the scale, but also the growth rate of the population is mind-boggling lol In particular, the first doubling will take place in 700 years, and the second - in 150 in a year, the third in 100 years and the last one in less than 40 years gave It should be noted that in the first decade of the 20th century on Earth 1 billion in total, 2.8 billion people lived on Earth in 1956, and 5 billion in 1985 In 2015 of the 21st century, the total number of people living on earth was 7.5 billion exceeded. According to futurologists, there will be more than 15 billion people on earth in 2050 is predicted to live.

The so-called "demographic explosion" of the world's population in the 20th century is unprecedented growth is not biological laws, but spontaneous, uneven social development and the abyss that humanity is trying to overcome with great difficulty was a product of social conflicts. This applies primarily to developing countries and account for more than nine-tenths of world population growth will come. The situation here was typical of developed countries at the beginning of the

20th century the high death rate and birth rate typical of the 18th century for all mankind characterized by a high level.

At the same time, the level of labor productivity and per capita to the amount of income, the level of productivity of agricultural crops and the village efficiency of the economy, literacy level of the population and general cultural according to the level, most of the peoples of these countries are still living in the 19th century.

Demographic problems are too complex and persistent to be solved quickly can't be reached. The longer their solution is delayed, the more complicated and it gets more complicated. For this reason, all governments in developing countries to implement a demographic policy aimed at reducing the birth rate is trying For example, in Uzbekistan in 1995, "Family Planning" was implemented program was accepted. Plan the birth of a child in each family in this program It is one of the efforts aimed at protecting the health of mother and child in line, it is planned to gradually implement the task of preventing the demographic explosion in the country. In this regard, in all regions, villages and Promotional work on reproductive health is being carried out in villages. That's it It should be noted that the average age of the population in Uzbekistan during the years of independence 73 years for men, 75 years for women. This problem has developed countries, but to face its reflection here possible Even in the process of increasing life expectancy and the number of elderly people a decrease in the birth rate that does not provide even normal population growth being observed. In this case, about depopulation, that is, about the decrease in the population it is said that (the average age of the population of Russia is 54 years old), this is also national benefits, implementation of social programs, pension provision and the like creates additional difficulties. of the last 20 years in Russia demographic processes are a clear example of this. However, in the next five years it is positive changes are being observed in the matter. Including population growth and average life expectancy increased to 4 years. The problem of education. The reasons for the demographic explosion are connected with the problem of education depends. In recent years, the number of illiterate people in the world has decreased by percentage. continues to

grow in absolute terms. This is the life of uneducated people to archaic family traditions that actually justify many children with superstitious beliefs obeys. Finally, the difference between developed and developing countries continues to increase in this respect. Observing a strange situation at the moment possible: at a time when literacy is growing in absolute numbers, the illiterate, i.e and the number of people who do not know how to read, write, perform simple arithmetic operations is growing (70% of the population of India, 60% of the population of Pakistan, Africa 80% of the population of the countries are illiterate). In addition, the level of education of most people is new In today's society, a wide user of technology and computer equipment functional related to not allowing full life and work illiteracy is also growing. Another aspect of this problem is that in most countries of the world, the opportunity to get education is equal to everyone is not provided, which is an additional source of social tension. Also, improving the quality of education and its content at the present time the issue of socialization is transverse. To emphasize that The socialization of education should include the study of humanities in the educational process not to increase the hours or the number of subjects, but the content of natural sciences humanitarianization, any scientific discovery to protect human interests should direct. Only then is a person able to preserve his existence will be. In this regard, the "Personnel" adopted in Uzbekistan in

1997 in the National training program" expresses exactly these goals. "In Uzbekistan Annual expenditure on education is 10-12% of GDP constitutes.

However, in world experience, this indicator does not exceed 3-5 percent"1. Because it is social for a person not only to acquire knowledge, but also to acquire professional skills is an important factor in eliminating illiteracy.

Summary:

In short, there are various things that are happening all over the world and in the life of our country detailed information about the problems is given and these problems

are divided into three groups can be separated. First, including here, the elimination of war from the life of society achieve and ensure a just world; two, such as the establishment of a new international economic order A very important problem is distinguished. The second group is the interaction of society and nature resulting problems, which deprive people of energy, fuel, supply of fresh water, raw material resources, etc. This environmental problems to the group, as well as mastering the World Ocean and outer space also includes The third group consists of problems related to the "man-society" system demography problem, healthcare, education, threat of international terrorism spiritual issues and the like to seek solutions to similar problems research is being conducted.

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